

Demonstrating solar hydrogen evolution using thiomolybdate-modified carbon nitrides in a mass transport intensified 3 L loop photoreactor – A feasibility study

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Abstract

In this work, the feasibility of natural solar light-driven hydrogen production is demonstrated for a 3 L stirred loop photoreactor (SLPR) with thiomolybdate (Mo_3S_{13})-loaded carbon nitride particles (CN_x) as a heterogeneous photocatalytic model system. To ensure sufficient irradiance incident to the slurry-type SLPR, a combined specular/diffuse solar collector was designed and evaluated using ray tracing simulations, resulting in an increase of the irradiance incident to the SLPR by a factor of 2.4 compared to operation of the SLPR without a reflector. The combined specular/diffuse solar collector was optimized for $\lambda < 400$ nm to meet the photophysical properties of CN_x . Solar hydrogen production rates of ≈ 97.1 - $111.5 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ could be demonstrated. Solar hydrogen production rates were found to correlate with the incident solar irradiance.

Introduction

Climate change as a major challenge of the 21st century has attracted global attention after the Paris agreement of 194 nations and the European Union on the reduction of the global temperature increase to well below 2 °C compared to the pre-industrial levels^[1,2]. Considering steadily rising global CO₂ emissions, the narrow window of opportunity to reach the set climate targets requires the elaboration of strategies to mitigate the reliance on fossil fuels^{[3,4][5,6]}. Nevertheless, the rising global energy demand (650 EJ in 2024) must be satisfied to face the challenges of rapid population and economic growth^[7]. Solar energy with a yearly global supply of $3.8 \cdot 10^8$ EJ, offers the greatest potential amongst renewable energy sources to meet this challenge while addressing climate change and emission mitigation^[8,9].

Solar fuels such as H₂ generated from water splitting, along with value-added chemicals such as hydrocarbons from CO₂ reduction and NH₃ from N₂ reduction, represent a promising foundation for a green and sustainable economy^[10]. Based on its high energy density of 120 MJ · kg⁻¹, hydrogen represents an attractive alternative to fossil fuels^[11,12]. The direct photocatalytic conversion of solar energy to hydrogen can be achieved by overall water splitting ($\Delta G^\circ = +237 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)^[13] and organic reforming reactions. Alcohols like methanol, ethanol and isopropanol are commonly used as sacrificial agents and enhance the photocatalytic hydrogen production, as they capture holes and can therefore concentrate the electrons required for the reduction half reaction ($\Delta G^\circ = -121.6 - 127.4 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$).^[14] Using alcohols derived from biomass, e.g., furfuryl alcohol or 5-hydroxymethylfurfural photocatalytic hydrogen production and alcohol oxidation can be coupled to form value-added chemicals like aldehydes and acids^[15]. Independent of the use of sacrificial agents, which improve photocatalytic efficiencies in comparison to pure water splitting, photocatalytic solar hydrogen production efficiencies remain rather low (1-2 % or less)^[16-18] compared to the feasibility threshold estimates of 5-13 %^[19,20].

The overall efficiency of a light-driven photochemical process depends on the used photochemical reaction system and radiation field, requiring efficient absorption of the incident light, efficient charge separation and transfer as well as the mitigation of charge recombination.^[21] Long-term stability, recyclability of catalysts, as well as reasonable costs of the used components together with the achievable hydrogen production rates determine the economic feasibility for the application in solar hydrogen production.^[22] In addition to the chosen reaction systems, the overall performance in solar hydrogen production depends strongly on the reactor choice (high degree of light transmission, sufficient mass- and heat transfer properties) and the photon flux incident to the photoreactor.^[23] Therefore, the key to realize solar fuel production is a tailored combination of highly active, stable and economically feasible catalysts with scalable photoreactor concepts and suitable solar collectors^[13,19,24-26].

Solar photoreactors using suspended photocatalysts for solar hydrogen production are projected to be cost-competitive with fossil fuels^[27]. Even though particulate photocatalysis suffers from relatively low efficiencies (1-2 %) compared to photoelectrochemical conversion (efficiency 2 - 19 %), there is a major advantage for application in the direct solar-to-fuel conversion based on its low system complexity^[10,14,26]. The system's simplicity has limitations. High particle-induced scattering effects reduce the penetration depth of light into the reactor. Therefore, a slurry-type reactor must ensure sufficient mixing to counteract reaction-rate gradients induced by light penetration, which requires additional energy to ensure suspension stability^{[26][28,29]}. Especially for higher suspension densities ($> 1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$), hydrogen production rates cannot be simply increased proportionally with higher suspension loadings since the resulting strong decrease of the local volumetric rate of photon absorption (LVRPA) leads to extended shadowed volumes of the reactor that do not contribute to any performance improvements^{[30][31][32,33]}. Examples for slurry-type photoreactors for hydrogen production are mostly limited to laboratory scale and simple solar demonstrator reactors^[30-33]. However, Cao et al. demonstrated photocatalytic hydrogen evolution using (Na_2S and Na_2SO_3) as sacrificial agents in a slurry-type tubular reactor equipped with compound parabolic reflectors with a production of 10.321 L h^{-1} under a mean solar radiation of 803.8 W m^{-2} but described major issues in suspension stabilization during operation.^[34]

The spectral solar energy distribution approximately splits to 4 % ultraviolet (UV), 42 % visible (vis), and 54 % infrared irradiation^[28]. The useful range of solar wavelengths for photochemical reactions is dictated by the absorbable wavelength range of the used photocatalysts. Typically, photocatalysts are active in the UV and partly in the visible wavelength spectrum. Therefore, only a minor share of the solar energy is available for the photochemical conversion^[26,35]. Various concepts for solar collection devices including, parabolic trough, dish and linear Fresnel reflectors and solar power towers have been proposed in literature to address the fluctuating availability of solar light^{[36,37] [38,39]}. These concepts can only concentrate direct radiation with high concentration factors of up to 100, but require a tracking system to account for the changing position of the sun^[23,40]. Due to the high concentration factors, a suited thermal management is essential to avoid undesired temperature changes. Compound parabolic collection devices do not require tracking, since diffuse light can be captured but can only realize lower solar concentration factors of 2-5^[40,41]. Furthermore, thermal management is simpler due to the reduced heat input. Appropriate reflector concepts must be chosen based on the required concentration factors and the required degree of irradiation homogeneity and geometrical characteristics of the photoreactor. A "one-size-fits-all" solution for solar collection devices is usually not feasible due to the varying demands of different reaction systems and corresponding photoreactor concepts, emphasizing the need for efficient strategies for reflector design and optimization.

Raytracing is a powerful tool for the design, optimization and development of tailored collector devices that can be used to develop collectors tailored for a specific use case and can help to maximize the efficiency of the solar-to-fuel conversion^[42-45].

Recently, a stirred loop photoreactor (SLPR) has been applied on the 0.5 L scale with platinum-loaded polymeric carbon nitride particles (CN_x) for hydrogen production under UV irradiation using 365 nm LEDs^[46]. Beránek et al. demonstrated the feasibility of Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃]·5 H₂O (**{Mo₃}**) loaded CN_x (**{Mo₃}**-CN_x) for hydrogen evolution (HER) as a molecular alternative to Pt as co-catalyst on the low mL laboratory scale.^[47] Molybdenum-based catalysts for HER are a widely discussed cost-efficient alternative to Pt due to the approximately three orders of magnitude lower costs of Mo and high HER activity^[48-51]. The larger scale applicability of the **{Mo₃}**-CN_x reaction system was showcased by Ziegenbalg et al. in a scaled 3 L SLPR^[52]. Therefore, this study aims at demonstrating the feasibility of natural light-driven HER using **{Mo₃}**-CN_x in a slurry-type scaled 3 L SLPR. Since the HER activity of the **{Mo₃}**-CN_x reaction systems heavily depends on the wavelength (high activity in the UV range, low activity in the visible range)^[47] and intensity of the available solar irradiation the SLPR was integrated with a solar collector to reach a high concentration factor in the relevant wavelength range (< 400nm).

Photoreactor Setup and Performance Metrics

Stirred Loop Photoreactor Concept

Various studies on particle-based photocatalytic hydrogen production revealed major limitations of small-scale laboratory slurry-type photoreactors for operation at higher slurry densities ($\approx 1 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$)^[30,31]. To counteract this issue, mass transport intensification (intense stirring or fluidization) can be applied to increase hydrogen production rates^[32,33]. Therefore, the scaled 3 L SLPR, which was already applied successfully for $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ -CN_x based hydrogen evolution with artificial light sources, was chosen for solar feasibility studies (see Figure 1)^[52].

The SLPR realizes internal recycling of the reaction solution through forced convection

through the internal draft tube and the outer annular region of the reactor. By this catalyst particles are moved from the centre of the reactor (shadowed dark region) towards the irradiated annular region while ensuring a high suspension quality. In addition, inert gas

Figure 11: Picture of the SLPR (left), SLPR dimensions in mm (middle) and corresponding schematic depiction of the SLPR working principle (right). SLPR: Stirred Loop Photoreactor, SC: Solar Collector.

can be purged through the reactor, which was found to significantly improve the hydrogen production for Pt-CN_x photocatalyst^[46]. The 3 L SLPR is manufactured from borosilicate glass (thickness $\approx 2 \text{ mm}$) and consists of four modular parts (bottom part, middle part with removable draft tube and top part) enabling connectivity to purge gas and cooling liquid supply as well as coupling to an overhead stirrer. The actual reactor part containing the reaction solution (diameter 96 mm, height $\approx 390 \text{ mm}$) can be filled with 3 L of reaction solution.

Solar Collector Concept

Figure 2: 3 L SLPR under solar operation (right), picture of the developed combined specular/diffuse collector (middle) and schematic depiction of the reflector working principle (left).

To guide photons efficiently to the $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ reaction system within the SLPR, a combined specular/diffuse solar collector (SC) was developed (see Figure 2, left). The SC was optimized using raytracing simulations for a spectral range $\lambda < 400$ nm, adjusted to the photophysical properties of CN_x . To reduce the geometrical complexity of the SC and corresponding reliance on specialized manufacturing techniques, a specular collector component consisting of two mirrors and a diffuse component made from a PTFE sheet were combined (see Figure 2, right). With this, both specular and diffuse fractions of the incident solar radiation are guided towards the reactor to enable SPLR operation without the necessity of SC tracking.

Performance Metrics

To analyze the performance of the SLPR, the following performance metrics were determined

- a) The mean hydrogen evolution rate $r_{\text{H}_2, \text{mean}}$

$$r_{\text{H}_2, \text{mean}} = \frac{n_{\text{H}_2}}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

- b) The turnover number TON

$$\text{TON} = \frac{\Delta n_{\text{H}_2}}{n_{\text{cat}, \text{active}}} \quad (2)$$

- c) The turnover frequency TOF

$$\text{TOF} = \frac{d \text{TON}}{d t} \quad (3)$$

- d) The efficiency of the collector $\eta_{\text{Collector}}$ which relates the total incident solar power at the receiver planes of the SC $P_{\text{solar UV, receiver}}$ (top and front, see Figure 4 c) to the power received at the reactor surface $P_{\text{solar UV, reactor}}$ for $\lambda < 400$ nm.

$$\eta_{\text{Collector}} = \frac{P_{\text{solar UV, reactor}}}{P_{\text{solar UV, receiver}}} \quad (4)$$

- e) The solar conversion efficiency SCE, which considers the Gibbs free enthalpy for HER $\Delta G_{\text{MeOH reforming}}^{\circ}$ using methanol as a sacrificial agent and the total solar power incident to the receiver $P_{\text{solar,receiver}}$

$$\text{SCE} = \frac{r_{\text{H}_2,\text{mean}} \cdot \Delta G_{\text{MeOH reforming}}^{\circ}}{P_{\text{solar,receiver}}} \quad (5)$$

- f) The apparent quantum efficiency AQE using the absorbed solar photon flux $q_{\text{solar UV,absorbed}}$

$$\text{AQE} = \frac{r_{\text{H}_2,\text{mean}}}{q_{\text{solar UV,absorbed}}} \quad (5)$$

- g) And the external photonic efficiency ξ_{ext} using the absorbable photon flux $q_{\text{solar,UV,receiver}}$ incident to the receiver plane.

$$\xi_{\text{ext}} = \frac{r_{\text{H}_2,\text{mean}}}{q_{\text{solar UV,receiver}}} \quad (6)$$

$q_{\text{solar,UV,receiver}}$ and $q_{\text{solar UV,absorbed}}$ can be estimated for a polychromatic emitter if a normalized spectral emission ($s(\lambda)$) of a light source with $\int_{\lambda_{\text{min}}}^{\lambda_{\text{max}}} s(\lambda) d\lambda = 1$ is known from the optical power (P_{rad}) of the radiation source with $s(\lambda)$ and the integration limits of the emission spectrum $[\lambda_{\text{min}}, \lambda_{\text{max}}]$ (Eq. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**)

$$q_{\text{solar,UV}} = \frac{P_{\text{rad}}}{N_{\text{A}} \cdot h \cdot c} \cdot \int_{\lambda_{\text{min}}}^{\lambda_{\text{max}}} s(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda \quad (7)$$

Results and Discussion

Combined Specular/Diffuse Solar Collector Concept

The combined specular/diffuse solar collector was designed with the help of raytracing simulations to maximize the optical solar power incident to the SLPR at midday sun. Weather data recorded over a period of three months (July-September) at the setup location was used to determine the optical power absorbed by the reactor medium under the assumption of full absorption. Using the irradiation profile of the recorded weather data, an integral incident

Figure 3: **a** Incidence profile (Gleisdorf, Austria) July-September 2025, **b** 3D CAD model used for raytracing simulations, **c** depiction of the receiver plane.

solar energy of $1 \text{ W} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ could be determined. For the UV spectral range ($\lambda < 400 \text{ nm}$), the simulations - based on average recorded weather data over three months - revealed an absorbable optical power of 31.6 mW incident to the reactor without a solar collector and 75.7 mW, with a solar collector, representing a 2.4-fold increase of the available optical power. To obtain representative mean optical powers at the reactor surface, the integrated daily incident solar energies, recorded for the trial days, were averaged over 24 h, including night-time, resulting in mean diurnal optical powers of 8.1 W (without collector) and 20.2 W (with collector) for 19.09.2025, and 6.8 W (without) and 17.1 W (with) for 22.09.2025, reflecting the collector's enhancement factor of 2.4. These values were then used to normalize the experimentally measured time-resolved solar power profiles, preserving the diurnal distribution while ensuring consistency with the irradiation model. Resulting in corrected mean powers ($P_{\text{solar,UV,reactor}}$) incident to the reactor surface for the duration of the experimental trials of 7.31 W (19.09.25) and 6.85 W (22.09.25). Using the normalized spectral solar emission ($\lambda < 400 \text{ nm}$, AM 1.5)^[28], absorbed solar photon flux ($q_{\text{solar,UV,absorbed}}$) was calculated as $21.78 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (19.09.25) and $20.41 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (22.09.25), assuming full absorption by the reactor surface (details in ESI, Section 4.3).

ξ_{ext} calculations were based on the incoming solar irradiance, measured for the respective experimental trial days, for the two relevant sub-surfaces front ($A = 0.381 \text{ m}^2$) and top ($A = 0.256 \text{ m}^2$) (see Figure 4 c) of the receiver and converted to temporal optical powers

based on the isotropic sky model (see section 4.2 ESI). Corresponding optical powers ($P_{\text{solar UV,receiver}}$) in the UV region ($\lambda < 400$ nm, considering AM1.5 spectral distribution) of 20.35 W (19.09.25) and 19.30 W (22.09.25), with $q_{\text{solar,UV,receiver}}$ of $60.64 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (19.09.25) and $57.51 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (22.09.25) were determined. A mean $\eta_{\text{Collector}}$ of 35.72 % ($\lambda < 400$ nm) can be calculated using $P_{\text{solar UV,receiver}}$ and $P_{\text{solar,UV,reactor}}$ according to Eq. (4).

SCE were calculated based on the mean total solar power incident to the sub-surfaces of the receiver ($P_{\text{solar,receiver}}$) of 361.64 W (19.09.25) and 341.21 W (22.09.25) determined for the duration of the trials.

Feasibility of Photocatalytic Solar Hydrogen Production using $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$

Figure 4: Hydrogen production rates for the conducted trials 1 and 2 (19.09.25 and 22.09.25) and alignment with corresponding measured solar irradiance.

$\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ loaded CN_x particles were studied for solar H_2 production in two consecutive experiments (19.09.25 and 22.09.25) using the SLPR with a total internal volume of ≈ 2.8 L. SLPR operation was initiated at midday sun to meet the required solar intensities for the feasibility studies. The performance of each experimental trial was evaluated based on the solar hydrogen production rate and correlated to the solar irradiance data measured (see Figure 5). A proportional decrease of the hydrogen production rate with a decreasing

solar irradiance, declining rapidly after solar noon, was observed. Maximal solar hydrogen production rates of $r_{\max} = 97.1$ and $r_{\max} = 111.5 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ were found for the first and the second day, respectively. SEM/EDX characterization of the $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ particles revealed a Mo cluster loading of 1.1 at% (w/w), which is corresponding to 2.6 wt% $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ loading (see ESI Figure 5), with which TONs of 2.03 and 3.09 and TOFs of 0.0086 min^{-1} and 0.0081 min^{-1} were calculated for the two days. A performance comparison of the conducted solar hydrogen production trials with laboratory experiments is shown in Table 1. In a laboratory experiment carried out over 7 h under constant irradiation with a 420 nm LED (irradiance: $500 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$, power: 2.0 W, volumetric photon flux: $0.0703 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) on the 10 mL scale (slurry density $1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) in a stirred 21 mL Schlenk tube a TON of 24.9 with a corresponding TOF of 0.0592 min^{-1} was calculated^[47]. In comparison, a significant decrease of TON (2.03 and 3.09) by more than 85 % under solar operation of the SLPR was observed. This observation is a result of the decreasing temporal solar irradiance for the solar and the trials low mean solar irradiance ($38.27\text{-}40.84 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$, power: 20.41-21.78 W, volumetric photon flux: $0.0073\text{-}0.0079 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$, $\lambda < 400 \text{ nm}$) incident to the reactor surface. 3 L SLPR laboratory experiments under constant irradiation with 365 nm LEDs (irradiance: $184.96 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$, power: 21.21 W, volumetric photon flux: $0.0225 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$), resulted in a mean TON of 35.9 and TOF of 0.021 min^{-1} for an operational time of 27.85 h. For the solar trials, the shorter operational time must be considered (4-6 h vs. 27.85 h). Assuming a similar activity behavior under artificial and natural irradiation, a 3 to 4 times higher TON can be expected for longer reaction times. The mean TOF (0.0086 min^{-1} and 0.0081 min^{-1}) were also found to be lower under natural solar irradiation, which is a result of the on average about 3.1-times lower incident photon flux under natural solar irradiation.

Table 1: Performance comparison of photocatalytic hydrogen production using $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$.

Reactor	irrad	V / mL	$\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x / \text{g}$	t / h	$\text{H}_{2,\text{total}} / \mu\text{mol}$	$r_{\text{mean}} / \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$	$\xi_{\text{ext}} / \%$	SCE / %	AQE / %	TON / 1	TOF / min^{-1}
3 L SLPR 19.09.25	solar	2800	3.0	3.95	224.8	56.91	0.026	$2.78 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.073	2.03	0.0086
3 L SLPR 22.09.25	solar	2800	3.0	6.37	341.8	53.69	0.026	$2.78 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.073	3.09	0.0081
3 L SLPR	365 nm	2880	2.88	27.85	3816.9	137.05	0.059	n.a.	0.059	35.9	0.021
Schlenk tube	420 nm	10	0.01	7	3.0	0.43	0.019	n.a	0.019	24.9	0.0592

Table 2: Comparison of irradiation characteristics of the reactors used for hydrogen production using $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$.

Reactor	spectral irradiation	A / m^2	I / $\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$	P / W	q / $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	$q_{\text{vol}} / \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$
3 L SLPR 19.09.25	solar < 400 nm	0.179	40.84	7.31	21.78	0.00778
3 L SLPR 22.09.25	solar < 400 nm	0.179	38.27	6.85	20.41	0.00729
3 L SLPR	365 nm	0.115	184.96	21.21	64.71	0.0225
Schlenk tube	420 nm	0.004	500.00	2.0	7.03	0.0703

For the solar trials mean hydrogen production rates were found to be larger by a factor of 125-132 in comparison to the 10 mL scale laboratory experiments. Interpretation of these results has to consider the volumetric scale-up by a factor of 300, which also increased the outer surface of the reactor and thus the available photon flux. To consider these changes, laboratory experiments conducted in the 3 L SLPR with artificial irradiation (365 nm) must be compared to the natural solar irradiation results. For this comparison, decrease of the mean hydrogen production rates by about 68.7-70.5 % was found, which correlate with the about 78.6 % decreased irradiance for the solar trails in comparison to the laboratory experiment. Hence, the decreased mean reaction rates observed for the solar trials are reasoned by a photonic limitation of the catalytic activity and the significantly lower solar photon flux incident under solar operation. The photonic performance of the solar trials can be compared to the laboratory experiments using ξ_{ext} . For the conducted solar trials ξ_{ext} of 0.026 % was determined, comparable to the laboratory experiments conducted on the 10 mL scale. For the larger scale laboratory experiments (3 L SLPR) ξ_{ext} of 0.059 % was determined, also aligning well with the solar trials considering $\eta_{\text{Collector}}$ of 35.72 %. Due to the high absorption degree of the suspension (≈ 1) in the laboratory trials AQE can be approximated to be equal to ξ_{ext} . Taking $\eta_{\text{Collector}}$ into account, the optical power incident to the reactor is significantly lower compared to the receiver plane, leading to a higher AQE of 0.073 % for the solar trials. Considering the total solar power incident to the reactor surface, a SCE of $2.78 \cdot 10^{-4}\%$ is observed for the solar trials. The low SCE can be explained by the poor absorption properties of the used CN_x particels within the vis region of the solar spectrum. SCE calculations were based on a $\Delta G_{\text{MeOH reforming}}^{\circ} = +63.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ considering the partial oxidation of methanol to formaldehyde with simultaneous hydrogen evolution as the relevant overall reaction (for details see ESI section 5).

To further improve the performance of solar hydrogen production using $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$, various optimizations strategies must be considered. The high suspension densities used to compare the system performance to laboratory experiments must be adapted to the reactor scale to ensure optimal operating conditions. In laboratory experiments using $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ suspensions in the 3 L SLPR no improvements of the hydrogen production rates could be observed at suspension densities $> 0.66 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$. It is therefore expected that a reduction of the suspension density tailored to the reactor scale will not lower hydrogen production rates, but increase the photonic efficiency of the process at a constant hydrogen production rate^[53]. The upright positioning of the SLPR, required to ensure internal looping and sufficient mixing to realize a high suspension quality, raises major challenges for solar operation and requires repositioning of the SC during operation. While the SLPR was primarily chosen to enable a comparison with laboratory experiments, it depicts a suboptimal concept for solar operation with static SC. During the conducted trials a maximal solar photon flux of around

81.77 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ ($\lambda < 400 \text{ nm}$) incident to the receiver surface was determined, comparable to the 3 L SLPR laboratory experiments of 64.71 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ ($\lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$). Thus, it can be expected that optimized solar collectors will provide high photon irradiance and ensure solar operation comparable to artificial lighting^[40,41]. In addition, other mass transport intensified photoreactor concepts like tubular oscillatory baffled reactors (OBR)^[54–58] could be implemented. OBR can be operated at more favorable operations angles relative to the incoming solar irradiation than the SLPR. A coupling with compound parabolic collectors might provide both a sufficed irradiation and suspension quality. Since the used **{Mo₃}**-CN_x reaction system efficiently absorbs photons only within the UV region but suffers from poor absorptive properties within the VIS region of light, strategies to expand the absorption of the used reaction system towards the visible region can be another viable approach to enhance the system performance at solar operation. Altering CN_x absorption properties or alternatively linking suited catalysts to PS to create PS-cat dyads to enhance absorption within the visible region have been reported by literature.^[59–61] Besides this, the effect of dynamic irradiation on the overall performance, which is induced by the hydrodynamics in the SLPR have to be understood in more detail to tailor operation conditions towards highest performance^[62,63].

Conclusions and Outlook

The presented experimental results demonstrate the feasibility of solar hydrogen production using **{Mo₃}**-CN_x in a slurry-type 3 L SLPR for the first time. It could be shown that **{Mo₃}**-CN_x represents a viable option for the application in solar hydrogen production, due to its long-term stability and relatively low cost. While the performance/efficiency of the SLPR for solar operation was found to be lower as for the laboratory experiments, this difference could be correlated to photonic limitation resulting from the significantly lower solar irradiance. It is expected that a similar performance of solar hydrogen production can be realized by providing a higher light intensity to the SLPR. Adaptions on the reactor level and precise tuning of operating conditions are required to improve the overall performance. In addition, more efficient utilization of photons in the vis region of the solar spectrum ($\lambda > 400 \text{ nm}$) can further improve the performance of solar hydrogen production but requires adaptations on the material level. The results clearly show that laboratory results obtained with artificial light sources, even when measured in scaled photoreactors, cannot simply be transferred to natural solar irradiation conditions.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals

All commercially available reagents and solvents were purchased from companies as follows: technical grade methanol: VWR, L-ascorbic acid: Apollo Scientific, 25 % Ammoniac: VWR. Reagents were used directly without purification. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and CN_x were synthesized following the procedure described in the sections below.

$[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ Synthesis and $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ - CN_x Preparation

$\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and CN_x synthesis and subsequential catalyst loading to the CN_x was carried out according to the procedure described in the ESI (section 3). ATR-FTIR characterization data of the used catalyst and can be found in the ESI (Figure 6). SEM/EDX characterization data of the $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ loading can be found in in the ESI (Figures 3-5).

Experimental Procedure $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ - CN_x Catalysis and Loop Reactor Operation

The SLPR setup was placed on the rooftop of the solar testing facility (AEE INTEC, Gleisdorf Austria) and aligned to the south corresponding to the highest solar irradiance at midday sun. First, 52.836 g of ascorbic acid ($0.1 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) were dissolved in 1 L of deionized water and 300 mL of methanol were diluted with deionized water to a total volume of 2 L. Before filling, it was ensured that the gas inlet was closed at the reactor-side valve. The reactor was initially charged with 1 L of the ascorbic acid solution and subsequently filled up to the upper holding clamp (approximately 2.8 L total volume) with the methanol–water mixture. The cooling system was set to 10 °C and switched on, and the stirring speed was adjusted to 740 rpm. Then the gas inlet was opened and the gas flow was set to $200 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ with the mass flow controller. The system was inertized for approximately 20 min by purging gas through the reactor until no further peaks were detected in the GC signal. Subsequently, 3 g of catalyst ($1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) were added at reduced stirring speed, after which the stirring speed was reset to 740 rpm.

A detailed description of the used reactor setup can be found in in the ESI (Figures 1-2).

GC Analysis

Continuous GC analysis of H_2 was carried out using Argon 5.0 (99,9995 % purity) and a pressure of 5 bar at a sampling rate of 1 min^{-1} using a μGC (DynamiQ-S, Qmicro B.V.). The molar productions rates of H_2 were calculated using the ideal gas law based on a set argon flowrate through the loop reactor of $200 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, controlled by a mass flow controller (SFC5500-0.5slm, Sensirion).

Solar Collector/Concentrator.

The used collector consisted of two mirrors (coated aluminum collector, alanod, MIROSUN 20901L). As specular collectors and a diffuse collector component, a sheet manufactured from expanded polytetrafluoroethylene (GORE, Diffuse Reflector) with highly Lambertian reflectivity was used. The mirrors were placed on a 3D printed frame to ensure a curvature consistent with the CAD model used for the raytracing simulations and fixed by a wooden frame to ensure the structural stability of the collector. A detailed description of the used SC components can be found in in the ESI (Table 3).

Raytracing Simulations

Raytracing simulations were performed using Monte Carlo raytracing according to the RadiCal method proposed by Rüdissler^[64,65]. Raytracing simulations were based on the measured irradiation profile for the location (Gleisdorf, Austria) for the months of July to September provided in the ESI (solar_irradiance_July_September_Gleisdorf.csv).

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